

PRICE-VS-QUALITY COMPETITIVE TENDERS FOR THE PROCUREMENT OF HIGH-TECHNOLOGY MEDICAL DEVICES: STANDARDISING THE QUALITY SCORES ON A 0 TO 70 SCALE

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Introduction

The most recent guidelines in the procurement of high-tech medical devices recommend to take into account the clinical benefits generated by the therapeutic intervention. Complex techniques are available that provide an optimal methodological solution for this purpose. In particular, the net monetary benefit¹⁻⁷ (NMB) has emerged as the best technique that can be employed to analyse the clinical evidence available for the device under examination and to generate the quality score (on a scale 0 to 70) on the basis of the clinical benefit. At the same time, the NMB estimates the price score on scale 0 to 30 using compatible monetary units and,

in this way, allows for a comprehensive management of all computational phases needed to carry out the tender. The main drawback of the NMB approach is represented by its mathematical complexity and by the need to develop a specific computer program for each tender in order to adapt all calculations to the end-points that describe the clinical benefit for the specific disease condition. As a result, a simpler methodological approach is often needed. In general, in the absence of a software that executes all calculation based on a cost-effectiveness model, the traditional approach to manage a tender is to attribute the quality scores 0-70 based on the subjective judgement of a panel of experts (in most cases, the committee assigned the duty to manage the tender).

The main problem of this traditional approach is the excessive freedom that the experts are given in the assignment of quality-points. In the present report, we describe an experience conducted among 22 Italian experts in medical devices, that was aimed at suggesting pre-determined ranges of variation for each of the main items usually evaluated in modern quality assessments based on the clinical benefit. The purpose was to implement a reasonable flexibility in the assignment of these scores avoiding however all excessive scores that are not thought to be justified. By introducing these limitations, the traditional approach in managing these tenders is made more objective and more reproducible.

Methods

In December 2020, a group of 25 experts in medical devices were invited to participate in an online survey. These 25 experts were the members of a multiregional working group on medical devices formed in the first semester of 2020 by a national scientific society. This society (SIFACT, Società Italiana di Farmacia Clinica e Terapia -Italian Society for Clinical Pharmacy and Therapeutics-, Milano, Italy) included more than 1,000 professionals nationwide. A total of 22 responses to the questionnaire were obtained.

The questionnaire was intentionally kept as simple as possible (only 6 questions) and was subjected to approval by all participants. The text of individual questions can directly be seen in the Results section. The responses to the questionnaire were received during the last two weeks of December 2020.

Results

Table 1 summarises the contents of the questionnaire (including the text of the 6 questions) and presents the responses sent by the 22 participants. As expected, the magnitude of the clinical benefit ranked first in the score value (with an average of 21.5 points). The quality of the clinical evidence and the organisational impact ranked second and third, respectively. The last three places were occupied by innovative mechanism of action, favourable ergonomic features, and logistic advantages (such as storage at room or refrigerated temperature); these three items received around 6 to 7.5 points each.

Discussion

This report describes a very simple experience in an area where no data have yet been published. Hence, this is the main strength of the present short report. Firstly, since the sum of the 6 average values (Table 1) gives 69.3 points, these 6 items appear to be well representative of the main influencing the quality of medical devices in tenders. Further insight will be needed to more precisely determine the maximum and minimum values that can be suggested for each of the 6 items.

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Table 1. Questions included in the questionnaire and responses given by the 22 participants.				
Questions	No. of responses	Mean of responses	Range of responses	Suggested range to be used in tenders
1) How many points (0 to 70) would you recognise to "magnitude of the clinical benefit"?	22	21.5	15 to 40	0 to 23
2) How many points (0 to 70) would you recognise to "quality of the clinical evidence"?	22	15.0	10 to 25	0 to 16
3) How many points (0 to 70) would you recognise to favourable ergonomic features "?	22	6.8	5 to 12	0 to 8
4) How many points (0 to 70) would you recognise to "innovative mechanism of action "?	22	7.4	0 to 11	0 to 8
5) How many points (0 to 70) would you recognise to "favourable impact on the duration of the therapeutic/preventive intervention with favourable organisational consequences"?	22	12.6	7 to 20	0 to 13
6) How many points (0 to 70) would you recognise to "logistic advantages in management of the device"? (e.g. storage at room vs refrigerated temperature)	22	6.0	3 to 15	0 to 7

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